

DEVELOPING 4K COMPETENCIES IN TEACHING HISTORY (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE THEME OF THE SECOND WORLD WAR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17365457>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12th October 2025

Accepted: 14th October 2025

Online: 16th October 2025

KEYWORDS

history, education, 4C competencies, critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration, Second World War

ABSTRACT

The modern education system aims not only to provide knowledge but also to develop essential 21st-century competencies — critical thinking, creativity, communication, and collaboration (4C). In history teaching, the development of these skills promotes active student engagement, analytical thinking, reasoning, and teamwork. Using the topic of the Second World War as an example makes it possible to effectively integrate cognitive, educational, and practical aspects of learning, helping students become independent, creative, and responsible individuals.

As the education system rapidly develops today, the student's ability to think independently, their creative approach, and their ability to work effectively in a team are considered among the most important educational outcomes. Traditional educational models aim not only to provide education but also to transform the student into an active participant and unlock their personal potential. From this perspective, 4K competencies - critical thinking, creativity, communication, and collaboration - have become one of the priority areas of modern education.

Especially in the process of teaching history, the development of these competencies will equip students not only with historical knowledge, but also with analysis, thinking, and creativity. The ability to deeply understand historical events and evaluate them from different perspectives fosters a sense of civic responsibility and respect for human values in students.

In teaching the topic "World War II" in the 5th [1.127] grade of general education schools, the use of modern educational technologies and various graphic organizers contributes effectively to the development of 4C skills and enhances students' understanding of the topic.

4 C learning skills (critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration) were formed based on the 21st-century skills concept and were first introduced in the USA in 2002 by the Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21) organization. This model has been adopted as a key area of potential in modern education. [2]

1.Critical thinking is the student's ability to critically analyze information, identify the connection between events and phenomena, and draw conclusions by comparing various sources. This skill encourages the student to understand and evaluate the content of facts rather than memorizing them.

The following methods are effective for developing this competency in the context of World War II:

Activate thinking through questions:

What were the main causes of the war?

Which countries had the greatest influence on the outbreak of war, and why?

If diplomatic negotiations had been successful, how would history have changed?

What was the life of ordinary people during the war?

What was the main factor of victory?

Such questions as "why?," "how?," "if..." lead the reader to deep analysis and reflection.

The following graphic organizers can be recommended for developing this skill.

- The cause-and-effect diagram (Cause-Effect Chart) is used to determine the causes of war and the consequences of each cause.
- Venn Diagram To compare the interests and positions of different countries in the war.
- Fishbone (Ishikawa) diagram. To systematically show the factors that led to the Second World War.
- "T-table" (T-chart). To compare the positive and negative impacts of war.
- Cluster method. To systematize thoughts and ideas on the topic "War Lessons."

With the help of these organizers, students visually analyze information, engage in group discussions, and draw scientific conclusions.

Teaching methods:

- The "Debate" or "Historical Discussion" method teaches students to express their opinions from various perspectives.
- "Source Analysis" develops critical thinking through working with various historical documents and photographs.
- The "question-answer chain" deepens the thought by transitioning from one question to another.

2.Developing creativity. Creativity in teaching history is the student's creative approach to historical information, their ability to generate new ideas, and their ability to reassess events from various perspectives. This competence shapes the student not only as a perceiver of facts but also as a creative individual. Creative thinking on the topic of the Second World War can be developed in the following ways:

- Write an essay on the topic "If I lived during the war..."
- Create a poster or infographic on the topic "History Lessons for Peace";
- Showing historical events through a role-playing scene or a short video.
- "A Modern Approach to the Yalta Conference" - students will present a new diplomatic solution with their opinions and suggestions.

Graphic organizers:

Mind map - for the creative representation of connections between historical events or
Storyboard - for depicting war events in an illustrative sequence or
Timeline - for the creative visualization of the main stages of the war.

These methods enrich students' perspectives and allow them to perceive historical events through personal feelings and creativity.

3.Communication competence is the student's ability to express their thoughts clearly, reasonably, and culturally, and to listen to and understand the perspectives of others. In

history lessons, this skill engages students in active communication through discussion, debate, and collective reasoning.

Dobryakov (2011) emphasizes that tools for developing communicative competence include creative forms of activity, a system of non-traditional lessons, project activities, business games, and a set of tasks aimed at stimulating the need for communication. [3.119]

Methods of developing communication on the topic of the Second World War:

- Organize a role-playing discussion (debate) on the topic of the Yalta Conference or the Potsdam Accords.

- "Anti-war letter" - students express their thoughts and feelings about peace in written or oral form;

- "Press Conference of Historical Figures" - readers exchange opinions in the roles of Churchill, Roosevelt, Stalin.

Graphic organizers:

T-Chart - for comparing the positions and opinions of different historical figures;

Speech Map - for planning speech, formulating main points and arguments;

The question wheel is designed for systematically asking various questions during a conversation.

Through these activities, students develop their speaking skills, acquire the ability to justify their arguments and speak in public.

4. Collaboration - the ability of students to work in a team, share tasks, make decisions together, and strive for a common goal. This competency is crucial in teaching history because a comprehensive understanding of historical events is achieved through collective discussion and exchange of ideas.

For the development of cooperation on the topic of the Second World War:

- Group research works: "Traces of the War in the History of Uzbekistan," "The Role of Women and Children in War";

- Project method: Preparation of a group video or presentation on the topic "Peace and the Future of Humanity";

- "Collective History Map" - each group collects information about a specific country or front and creates a general map.

In developing collaboration, the use of the following graphic organizers can be significantly more effective.

- Project Planner - for the distribution of group tasks;

- Responsibility Chart - for defining the responsibilities of each member;

- Team Reflection Table - for evaluating results and drawing conclusions.

These activities nurture students as responsible individuals, open to collaboration, and ready to think collectively.

In conclusion, teaching history based on 4K competencies is an effective way to develop students' thinking and engagement in accordance with modern educational requirements. By utilizing the topic of World War II, students not only acquire historical knowledge but also develop skills in analysis, creative thinking, communication, and teamwork. This creates a solid foundation for their development as independent-thinking individuals with a responsible and civic position.

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